

ADMINISTRATIVE AND INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP OF SCHOOL HEADS AMONG INTEGRATED SCHOOLS

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Administrative and Instructional Leadership of School Heads among Integrated Schools

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Abstract

The goal of the research was to ascertain how instructional leadership practices, school heads' administrative success, and faculty members' teaching efficacy are related. In order to investigate the administrative performance and instructional leadership methods of school heads as well as the teacher performance level, the study used a descriptive-correlational research design and statistical techniques including mean, standard deviation, frequency count, and percentages. Spearman-Rank Order Correlation was used to ascertain the substantial relationship between school heads' administrative performance and teachers' teaching performance as well as between their instructional leadership techniques and teachers' teaching performance. The findings demonstrated that while teachers gave excellent education, school directors executed their administrative duties and instructional leadership methods to a "very high extent." Nonetheless, the efficacy of teachers' instruction is not greatly impacted by the administrative abilities or instructional leadership strategies of school heads. Hence, it was recommended that school heads should continue motivating teachers to sustain their exemplary teaching performance and continuously provide in-service training programs to intensify teaching proficiency.

Keywords: *administrative performance, instructional leadership practices, learners' services, human resource development programs*

Introduction

The thrust of The Department of Education to empower school heads and emphasize school-based management has increased and intensified. This is guided by the DepEd Order No. 17, s. 1997 which states the policy of empowering all public elementary and secondary school principals or school-in-charge in order to achieve desired higher learning outcomes. All school principals shall henceforth be vested with instructional administrative and fiscal autonomy for a more effective and efficient delivery of quality basic education.

School leadership is driven by the principle of quality results as DepEd's pushes its recent agenda on teachers' performance which is anchored on the tenets "Quality teachers in the Public school classrooms" with an ultimate goals of revisiting teachers' teaching performance in line with the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum of the Department of Education through the leadership of the school principals in all levels of the Philippine basic education.

The principles of Republic Act (RA) 9155, also referred to as the "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001," serve as the foundation for the administrative and instructional leadership of school heads in public schools. This act highlights the crucial role that school heads play in influencing the productive and successful performance of classroom teachers.

The complexity of the modern world brought about by scientific and technological advancements has altered many aspects of school administration, particularly in public secondary schools, including the working relationships and interpersonal dynamics among instructors as well as the workplace.

Effective and innovative management of instructional activities in public school require school heads who can truly inspire teachers to stimulate learners to learn and initiate change and innovations to make learning more interesting, rewarding, and meaningful.

The challenge facing public school administrators is to develop students who will soon assume leadership roles in society, transform more productive human organizations, and, above all, have the intelligence and creativity to advance the socioeconomic and political development of their nation. All of them, nonetheless, require the school heads' transformational leadership and efficient administration of the educational program.

Transformational school heads are those who can inspire and motivate teachers to continuously aspire for quality instruction and a leader who can recognize visible quality commitment from all their subordinates.

According to Aguilar (2018), the best approach to manage human resources in an organization is to support opportunities for people to advance their careers, give them the tools they need to succeed, help them adopt new technology, build more productive teams, and improve communication across the board.

According to Jaramillo (2017), one of the finest qualities of school heads is their capacity to mentor, oversee, and cultivate more successful team members inside the school system in order to meet the intended learning goals.

Therefore, in order to be administratively effective, school leaders must be able to effectively interact to and communicate with teachers and academic support staff, professionally handle both personal and professional issues, implement change, and encourage people to

be moral team players.

School heads in public secondary schools are responsible for transforming academic institution policies, plans, and programs into daily operations that support the achievement of the school's learning objectives. As instructional leaders, they must possess the attributes mentioned above.

The administrative tasks of planning, organizing, directing, staffing, coordinating, reporting, budgeting, decision-making, and human resource development are all crucial to the efficacy of instruction in public schools (Plunkett, 2005).

Studies have indicated that the execution of administrative duties is impacted by demographic variables, such as age, gender, level of education attained, academic standing, and length of time spent at the school leaders' respective academic institutions. Greaves (2005) has espoused that socio-demographic characteristics and a thorough understanding or knowledge on the administrative functions have the greatest influence to the school heads' administrative performance and instructional leadership.

However, issues on instructional leadership particularly in the areas of teachers' teaching effectiveness, training and development, promotion, students' misbehavior, and ancillary functions are some of the issues that may influence teachers' discouragement and work dissatisfaction which, in effect, stemmed to the subsequent sickness and even death of teachers is predominant.

This context is what motivated the researcher to conduct this study in order to determine the instructional and administrative leadership of heads of public integrated schools, who are in charge of providing public education that is both reasonably priced and of excellent quality.

Research Questions

The study sought to determine the influence of administrative performance and instructional leadership of school heads and the teachers' teaching performance of Opol East District, School School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the school heads' administrative performance in terms of:
 - 1.1. planning;
 - 1.2. organizing;
 - 1.3. directing; and
 - 1.4. controlling?
2. What is the school heads' instructional leadership in terms of:
 - 2.1. administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs;
 - 2.2. human resource development program; and
 - 2.3. students' services and development program?
3. What is level of teachers' teaching performance in terms of the following categories:
 - 3.1. outstanding;
 - 3.2. very satisfactory;
 - 3.3. satisfactory; and
 - 3.4. unsatisfactory?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' level of teaching performance and the schools heads' administrative performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' teaching performance and school heads' instructional leadership?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in the study was descriptive correlational. According to Calderon et al. (2012), descriptive research is an investigation or fact-finding inquiry. It is used to get in-depth understanding of the main reasons of the circumstances that are presented. In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry uses an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to an interview and observation.

Subsequently, descriptive research design will be used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis will be based on generated information from statistical tools.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adapted research questionnaires, paper surveys, interviews, and the like.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the school heads and teachers of Opol East District which is composed of 3- elementary schools ,

and 3-integrated schools , for the School Year 2022-2023.

There are six (6) school heads and one hundred eleven (111) elementary school teachers who will be taken as sample respondents. From the total population of one hundred twenty-five (125) teachers in six (6) schools , this study will take the one hundred eleven (111) as sample respondents based on the result computed using the Slovin- Formula.

Table 1 presents the number of teacher-respondents of six (6) schools of Opol East District, Misamis Oriental.

Table 1.

School	School Principal	Teachers	Total
Cauyunan IS	1	12	13
Malanang IS	1	14	15
Nangcaon IS	1	11	12
Binubongan ES	1	7	8
Igpit ES	1	43	44
Barra ES	1	24	25
Total	6	111	117

The study utilized the purposive sampling procedure for the school head-respondents and for the teacher-respondents of the study. In purposive sampling procedure we set out to identify members of the population who are likely to possess certain characteristics or experience.

Purposive sampling procedure is utilized for the school heads because there are six (6) elementary school heads of Opol East District, Division of Misamis Oriental, and same purposive sample procedure for the one hundred twenty-five (125) elementary teacher-respondents because teachers are of different strata in terms of school size, educational preparation, and grade level teaching. Although out of one hundred twenty-five elementary teachers (125) we use only one hundred eleven (111) as sample teacher-respondents based on the computed sample size for different population (N) at 0. .01 level of probability to a proportion 0.50

Creswell (2014) suggests being purposeful in identifying participants that might provide insight into your research question. Purposeful sampling involves selecting participants because you believe that they might contribute something to your analysis.

Instrument

The study utilized the survey questionnaire adapted from Dramayo (2014) on the administrative practices and instructional leadership effectiveness of school heads.

The survey questionnaire on administrative performance of school heads is composed of two parts. Part I is the administrative functions along the areas of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling functions of the school heads in Public Secondary Schools. The efficacy of school heads' instructional leadership is examined in Part 2 in three areas: student services and development, human resource development, and administration and supervision of instructional activities.

Procedure

For the school year 2022–2023, the researcher requested permission to conduct a study on the administrative performance and instructional leadership of school heads from the Division of Misamis Oriental Schools Division Superintendent. Following permission, the researcher began giving the study instrument to the principals and instructors of the six (6) public schools in the Opol East District. The research instruments was retrieved immediately after the respondents provided the data needed. Results were recorded, tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical treatment.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques are utilized in the study using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Problem 1. To determine the school heads' administrative performance, mean values and standard deviations were used.

Problem 2. To determine the school heads' instructional leadership, mean values and standard deviations were used.

Problem 3. To determine the teachers' teaching performance, frequency and percentage were used.

Problem 4. To ascertain the significant relationship between the teachers' teaching performance and the school heads' administrative performance , Spearman-rho was utilized.

Problem 5. To ascertain the significant relationship between the teachers' teaching performance and the school heads' instructional leadership, Spearman-rho was utilized.

Results and Discussion

This section contains the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the conclusion coming from the study on the administrative and

instructional leadership of school heads among integrated schools. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the problem presented.

Problem 1. What is the School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of: Planning, Organizing, Directing, and Controlling?

Table 2. Mean Distribution on School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of planning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Sets goals and objectives, workable Plans and programs of activities for the school.	4.66	.494	Very High Extent
2.) Determines the resources need Within the school.	4.74	.460	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.70	.477	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 2 displays the mean distribution of school heads' administrative performance in terms of planning. Overall, the respondents assessed the school head's administrative performance in terms of planning as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.70 (SD=.477). This score suggests that the school heads continually and permanently develop goals and objectives and viable plans and decides resources needed to attain school's goals and objectives.

The indicator "determines resources needed within the school" obtained the highest mean value of 4.74 (SD=.460) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that determining available resources and utilizing the same for the achievements of school's goals and objectives was predominantly practiced as part of the planning functions of the school heads in integrated schools. It can also be deduced based on findings that planning was highly practiced by the school heads to help achieve the goals and objectives of the school.

Saldana (2021) averred that the primary function of the school heads is to plan and determine resources needed in school to effectively and efficiently achieve schools' goals and objectives. Additionally, it was also accentuated that planning also involves making decisions about what resources are needed in order to provide the best educational services to the end beneficiaries of teaching-learning processes.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.66 (SD=.494) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "set goals and objectives, workable plans and programs of activities for the school". The result indicates that the school heads' planning function was enormously implemented especially in setting direction in achieving the educational plans and objectives of the learning institution. Thus, it is imperative that the school heads of the integrated schools should set goals and objectives and workable plans and programs of activities in both elementary and secondary levels simultaneously in order to ensure effective implementation of the same and achieve school's goals and objectives.

Parveen, et al (2021) avowed that school heads' ability to set goals and objectives and workable plans and programs of activities plays an important role in school heads' performance in leading the school organization and encouraging teachers to follow the set directions in school activities to ensure effective and efficient administrative performance.

Table 3. Mean Distribution on the School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of Organizing

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Identifies the work activities to be Done to accomplish the Objectives.	4.76	.444	Very High Extent
2.) Assigns the work to individual Teacher and delegate the appropriate Authority	4.80	.421	Very High Extent
3.) Recommends promotion or merit Increase in deserving teachers.	4.75	.450	Very High Extent
4.) Sends teachers or recommends to Seminars & in-service training.	4.61	.524	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.73	.459	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 3 displays the mean distribution of school heads' administrative performance in integrated schools in terms of organizing. Overall, the respondents rated the extent of the organizing function of the school heads as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.73 (SD=.459). This result indicates that the school heads exceptionally practiced organizing function in the school organization from assigning teachers the workload and delegating responsibilities based on their preparation, readiness, and work potentials. Additionally, school heads also conducted the professional development training programs for teachers, recommends for promotion to assigning and delegating responsibilities and ancillary assignments to teachers. It can be inferred based on findings that school heads organize all the resources in order to achieve the schools' goals and objectives.

The indicator "assigns work to individual teachers and delegate the appropriate authority" obtained the highest mean value of 4.80 (SD=.421) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which indicates that school heads in integrated schools constantly and permanently assign teachers' workload and delegate some responsibilities to deserving teachers as part of their organizing function. Thus, it is imperative that the school heads will always delegate responsibilities to teachers to develop their leadership skills and inspire them to unbridle their leadership potentials and capabilities.

Marzano (2021) pointed out that school heads who delegate administrative responsibilities inspire teachers to take tasks more earnestly and are motivated to perform their assigned tasks and workloads. It was also emphasized that assigning tasks and delegating responsibilities are administrative functions of the school heads which recognized teachers' leadership potentials.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.26 (SD= .524) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "sends teachers or recommends to seminars and in-service trainings". It can be deduced based on findings that school heads of integrated schools consistently recommend teachers for seminars and in-service training programs as part of the professional development programs of teachers.

Bredeson (2020) pointed out that school heads are mandated to provide trainings and professional development programs for teachers to enhance their teaching competence and proficiency in line with the Results-Based Performance Management System of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST).

Table 4. Mean Distribution on the School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of Directing

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Made policies, rules, and regulations For the internal operation of the School.	4.62	.522	Very High Extent
2.) Issues memo for teachers to follow The desired course of action.	4.81	.435	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.72	.479	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 4 displays the mean distribution of school heads' administrative performance in integrated schools in terms of directing. Overall, the respondents rated directing as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.72 (SD=.479). This result implies that the school heads in integrated schools extraordinarily exercise their administrative function of directing. The findings revealed that school heads made internal policies, rules and regulations for the internal operation of the school direct teachers through memoranda, notices and issuances for teachers' information and direction.

The indicator "issues memoranda for teachers to follow the desired course of action" obtained the highest mean value of 4.81 (SD=.435) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that school heads issue notices and memo for information and announcements to teachers.

Parveen, et al (2021) maintained that the most effective and efficient function of the school head is to direct performance of teachers through issuances of notice and memoranda to update and provide information to teachers of the activities of the school and to provide guidance and oversee the performance of teachers in order to achieve the predetermined goals. Additionally, it was emphasized that directing function of the school heads help create an appropriate work environment that facilitates efficient discharge of duties.

On the contrary, the indicator which states "made policies, rules and regulations for internal operation of the school" obtained the lowest mean value of 4.62 (SD=.522) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that in school heads always provide notices to teachers especially during meetings and conferences as communication mechanisms in school organization as part of the directing functions of school heads. It is imperative for the school head to initiate and outline policies, rules and regulations as well as issuances or notices to keep teachers informed and direct activities within the organization.

This finding was supported by Cheng and Tsui (2020) who affirmed that school heads performed administrative function in terms of directing to ensure that communication, instruction, supervision of teachers is guaranteed and to warrant that teachers are working towards the accomplishments of the school's goals and objectives.

Table 5. Mean Distribution on School Heads' Administrative Performance in terms of Controlling

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Steers performance towards desired Effective teaching results.	4.62	.522	Very High Extent
2.) Prepares timetable for the Accomplishment of the school.	4.81	.435	Very High Extent
3.) Supervises teachers to see if all Assigned tasks are done and Accomplished.	4.75	.450	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.73	.469	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 5 shows the mean distribution of school heads' administrative performance in integrated school in terms of organizing. Overall, the respondents rated the extent of the controlling function of the school heads as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.73 (SD= .469). This result indicates that the school heads in integrated schools remarkably practiced controlling function in school to ensure effective implementation and accomplishments of schools' activities and programs. It can be inferred based on findings that controlling function also guarantees proper resource allocations and utilization for the efficient and effective administrative and school performance.

The indicator "prepares timetable for the accomplishments of the school" obtained the highest mean value of 4.81 (SD= .435) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which indicates that school heads in integrated schools properly documented, accounted, and monitored all schools' activities and programs to ensure that all planned activities and programs are accomplished and necessary challenges are addressed. It can be construed based on finding that the school heads closely monitor all the schools' programs of activities through maintaining a timetable to ensure easy monitoring of its accomplishments.

This finding was supported by Marzano (2021) who suggests that school heads control schools' programs and activities to ensure its accomplishments as part of the learning experiences of school children.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.62 (SD= .522) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "steers performance towards the desired effective teaching results". It can be assumed based on findings that school heads inspire teachers to perform effectively to enhance teaching proficiency.

Tirana (2021) emphasized that school heads need to steer teachers' teaching performance through guiding them in improving teaching skills, to recognize and reinforce teaching excellence, to help them focus on student outcomes and achieving students' learning goals.

Problem 2. What is the school heads' instructional leadership in terms of: Administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs, Human Resource Development program, and Learners' services and development program

Table 6. Mean Distribution of the School Heads' Instructional Leadership in terms of Administration and Supervision of Instructional Activities and Programs

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Observes classes.	4.72	.469	Very High Extent
2.) Encourages teachers conduct Researches to enhance teaching Effectiveness.	4.76	.444	Very High Extent
3.) Provides necessary academic Counselling to teachers to Enhance teaching effectiveness.	4.83	.422	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.77	.445	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 6 shows the mean distribution of the school heads' instructional leadership in terms of administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs. Overall, the respondents rated the school heads' administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs as "Very High Extent" with a mean value of 4.77 (SD=.445). This result indicates that school heads extremely perform their functions in the areas of administration and supervision of instructional programs and activities which include monitoring of teachers in their instructional services, conduct of research activities to improve instruction, and to provide needed academic and instructional counselling to teachers to enhance teaching delivery, content, and learning assessment.

The indicator which state that "provide necessary academic counselling to enhance teaching effectiveness" obtained the highest mean value of 4.83 (SD=.422) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which indicates that school heads consistently provide academic counselling to teachers to enhance teaching proficiency and effectiveness.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.72 (SD= .469) which is verbally described as “Very High Extent” in the indicator “observes classes”. It can be reasoned based on findings that school heads constantly implement its instructional function of observing classes to ensure effective teaching performance which benefits the end-users of the teaching-learning processes. Archibong (2022) suggests that class observation allows the school head to monitor teachers’ teaching effectiveness and performance. Class observation is one of the administrative and supervisory technique for quality assurance and proactive means of guaranteeing quality in teaching.

Table 7. Mean Distribution of the School Heads’ Instructional Leadership in terms of Human Resource Development Program

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Conducts needs assessment to Teachers and academic support Personnel.	4.77	.459	Very High Extent
2.) Designs teachers and support Staff’s development programs.	4.75	.469	Very High Extent
3.) Encourages teachers to pursue Graduate and post-graduate Education.	4.58	.512	Very High Extent
4.) Recommends or sends teachers to Seminars, conferences, and Training.	4.68	.520	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.69	.49	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 7 depicts the mean distribution of the school heads’ instructional leadership in terms of human resource development program. With a mean score of 4.69 (SD=.49), the respondents evaluated the human resource development program as “Very High Extent” overall. This result denotes that the school heads predominantly underscored the development of human resources through teachers to training, seminars and conferences, graduate education, and the like.

The indicator “conducts needs assessment to teachers and academic support personnel” obtained the highest mean value of 4.77 (SD=.459) which is verbally described as “Very High Extent” which indicates that school heads always assess the needs of teachers and academic support personnel or the administrative officer and other office staff. It can be inferred based on findings that school heads stressed the importance of determining and addressing the needs for technical support for teachers and support staff to ensure work efficiency and effectiveness. Archibong (2022) asserted that school heads should always provide regular assessments on the needs of teachers and other school personnel in order to identify areas for improvement and personal development. It also helps teachers evaluate areas for improvement. It identifies gaps between the current conditions in a school and the desired conditions.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.58 (SD= .512) which is verbally described as “Very High Extent” in the indicator “encourages teachers to pursue graduate and post-graduate education”. It can be presumed based on findings that school heads always emphasized the importance of professional growth and development through graduate and post-graduate education. Thus, it is imperious for the school heads to encourage the teaching personnel to upgrade and take advantage of the infinite opportunities for professional development. Pineda (2022) pointed out that teachers need to be professionally upgraded by acquisition of advanced skills, knowledge, understanding and attitudes that will enable them to fulfill their potential in their current and future roles and help them work towards their career goals and to be more effective and efficient in their teaching.

Table 8. Mean Distribution of the School Heads’ Instructional Leadership in terms of Administration and Supervision of Learners’ Services and Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1.) Facilitates improvement of Media-resource center of the school.	4.77	.478	Very High Extent
2.) Encourages learners’ participation And collaboration in school and Community actions.	4.82	.429	Very High Extent
3.) Facilitates in the provision of Equipment for learners’ physical Developments such as sports and Athletics.	4.81	.436	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.80	.448	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 8 presents the mean distribution of the school heads’ instructional leadership in terms of learners’ services development program. Overall, the respondents rated the extent of the students’ services development program as “Very High Extent” with a mean value of

4.80 (SD=.448). This result implies that the school heads supported and prioritized the delivery of quality education by helping the school provides basic learners’ support services such as conducive learning environment and ensure learner’s readiness through the timely mobilization and equitable distribution of sufficient resources, provision of technical support.

The indicator “encourages learners’ participation and collaboration in school and community actions” obtained the highest mean value of 4.82 (SD=.429) which is verbally described as “Very High Extent” which implies that school heads ensure that learners participate and collaborate in school and community actions. This is to develop learners’ social awareness, builds teamwork, communication, relationships, and a sense of belonging, all of which help learners to develop socially and be successful in school. Cockpim and Somprach (2021) suggest that school heads’ function to provide support on learners’ services and development through encouraging learners to participate and collaborate in school activities and community involvement programs. This will help learners develop their social awareness skills and will help them enhance involvement in community activities and programs.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.77 (SD= .478) which is verbally described as “Very High Extent” in the indicator “facilitates improvement of media-resource center for the school”. This finding indicates that school heads helped and facilitated in the procurement and acquisition of media resources in school to better serve learners in their academic and learning needs. Archibong (2022) avowed that one of the responsibilities of the school heads is to facilitate the improvement of the schools’ media resources to better improve learners’ academic performance.

Problem 3. What is the level of teachers’ teaching performance in terms of the following categories: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and Poor?

Table 9. *Frequency Distribution of Teachers’ Teaching Performance*

Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	85	76.00
Very Satisfactory	27	24.00
Satisfactory	0	00.00
Unsatisfactory	0	00.00
Poor	0	00.00
Total	112	100.00

It can be asserted that out of 112 respondents, 85 (76%) had an “Outstanding” teaching performance while only 27 or 24% of the respondents had a “Very Satisfactory” teaching performance. This indicates that majority of the teachers performed immensely and levelheadedly in their teaching performance. It can also be averred that the higher number of teachers with outstanding teaching performance is attributed by the school heads’ ability to stimulate school resources such as the administration and supervision of instructional activities and programs, human resource development program, and learners’ services development program. This finding was supported by Murphy and Hallinger (2020) who exemplified that school heads’ administrative performance and instructional leadership contribute to teachers’ teaching efficiency.

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers’ level of teaching performance and the school heads’ administrative performance?

Table 10. *Significant Relationship Between the Teachers’ Level of Teaching Performance and the School Heads’ Administrative Performance*

Administrative Performance	Teachers’ Teaching Performance			
	(rs)	P-Value 2-tailed	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1
Planning	.032	.737	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted
Organizing	.111	.244	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted
Directing	.073	.444	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted
Controlling	.010	.915	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted

*significant at p<0.05 alpha level

Table 10 illustrates that there is minimal association between the administrative performance of school heads in terms of planning and the degree of teaching performance of teachers. This is demonstrated by the computed rs value of .032, which is lower than the p-value of .737. As a result, the null hypothesis held. The results suggest that there is no relationship between the administrative performance of school heads in terms of planning and the teaching performance of their instructors.

Further, school heads' administrative performance in terms of organizing denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident by the computed rs value of .111 which is lower than the p-value of .244. The null hypothesis was therefore accepted. Based on the results, it can be said that the administrative performance of school heads in terms of organization did not affect the quality of instruction provided by instructors. It can also be deduced that there are other variable that influence teachers' teaching performance other than the school heads' administrative performance in terms of organizing.

Furthermore, school heads' administrative performance in terms of directing denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident by the computed rs value of .073 which is lower than the p-value of .444. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers' teaching performance was not influenced by school heads' administrative performance in terms of directing.

Consecutively, school heads' administrative performance in terms of controlling negligibly correlated to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident by the computed rs value of .010 which is lower than the p-value of .915. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued understandably, that teachers' teaching performance was not influenced by the school heads' administrative performance in terms of controlling. Teachers' teaching performance can be attributed to other factors not mentioned in this study.

These findings were in contrary to the findings of Bas, et al, Bredeson, Cheng and Tsui (2020) and Parveen, et al., Tirana, and Saldana (2021) who pointed out that teachers' teaching performance was influenced by school heads' administrative performance in terms of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling functions. It can be averred credibly and astutely that teachers' teaching performance can be ascribed to other factors and variables not included in the study such as teachers' teaching dedication and commitment to the teaching profession, trainings and seminars attended, and educational preparations for the teaching position.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' teaching performance and the school heads' instructional leadership?

Table 11. *Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Performance and the School Heads' Instructional Leadership*

Instructional Leadership	Teachers' Teaching Performance			
	(rs)	P-Value 2-tailed	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1
Administration & Supervision Of Instructional Activities & programs	.129	.177	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted
Human Resource Dev. Programs	.055	.562	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted
Learners' Services & Development Program	.058	.545	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted

*significant at $p < 0.05$ alpha level

Table 11 presents the interplay between the school heads' instructional leadership and teachers' teaching performance. The table depicts that school heads' instructional leadership in terms of administration and supervision of instructional program denotes negligible correlation to teachers' teaching performance as evident in the computed rs value of .129 which is lower than the p-value of .177. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued that there is no significant relationship between the School Heads' Instructional Leadership practices in terms of administration and supervision of instructional programs and teachers' teaching performance.

In addition, school heads' instructional leadership in terms of human resource development program denotes negligible correlation to teachers' level of teaching performance as evident in the computed rs value of .055 which is lower than the p-value of .562. Hence, the

null hypothesis was accepted. It can be inferred based on findings that human resource development program of the school heads as component of their instructional leadership does not influenced teachers' teaching performance and effectiveness.

Moreover, school heads' instructional leadership in terms of learners' service and development program denotes negligible correlation to teachers' teaching performance as evident in the computed r_s value of .058 which is lower than the p -value of .545. As a result, the null hypothesis held. It is reasonable to argue that the effectiveness of teachers' instruction does not predict the availability of learners' services or other programs for their development. This implies that the instructional leadership roles that school heads play in terms of arranging for learners' services and other forms of development were not the driving forces behind teachers' proficiency and effectiveness.

These results were incongruous with those of Archibong (2022), Afandi (2023), and Cockpim and Somprach (2021), who astutely communicated, reported, and deduced from their research that the management and oversight of educational activities and programs; programs for developing human resources; and learner services and professional development initiatives of school administrators in the Philippines impacted the quality and efficacy of teaching among teachers.

The results of this study suggest that there are other variables or factors that affect teachers' performance in the classroom, such as rigorous pre-teacher education programs from universities and colleges, years of comprehensive teaching experience, personal and professional commitment to the teaching profession, and trainings, seminars, and conferences on teaching-learning strategies and methodologies.

Conclusions

From the findings, it was concluded that in general, that school heads' administrative performance and instructional leadership practices do not influence teachers' teaching performance effectiveness.

The study also concluded that there are factors that may influence and contribute to teachers' teaching performance effectiveness such as but not limited to the rigid pre-teachers trainings in colleges and universities where they obtained their education degrees, practical trainings or conferences and seminars workshops attended on teaching-learning methodologies and strategies, productive years of teaching in the public elementary schools, and teachers' personal dedication and commitment to the teaching profession are factors and variables that arguably and defensively define and describe teachers' level of teaching performance.

The following recommendations were made to be taken into consideration in light of the facts and conclusions that were presented:

School heads are stimulated to continuously encourage teachers to sustain teaching performance effectiveness through continuous professional development and in-service trainings on Safeguarding Education: Education Continuity Planning and the Whole-School Approach; Innovation in Education; Classroom Management: Uncovering Deeper Layers of Learning and Supporting Students with Learning Disabilities; and, demofest on educational innovation, technology and leadership.

Teachers need to sustain outstanding performance in order to benefit the end-users of the educational processes by intensifying positive attitude about teaching and learning amidst insurmountable challenges to always keep them focused and involved. Show enthusiasm, keenness and commitment to the calling of their teaching profession.

Similar investigation should likewise be conducted to ascertain factors that significantly influence teachers' teaching performance effectiveness.

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